

Ashanti

also known as “Akan”

Data source: eHRAF

Secondary source

Entered by Emily Pitek, Human Relations Area Files

** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: Religious Group, African Religions, Akan Religions

The Ashanti are an Akan people and have historically lived in south-central Ghana. This entry focuses on the Ashanti living in Kumasi state around the time of 1900, and largely relies on information from the principal ethnographic authority Robert Rattray (1923, 1927, 1929). At this time the basic social unit was the family group (localized matrilineage); various family groups came together under the head of one particular family to form territorial divisions or clans. Additionally, each individual belonged to one of two patrilineal exogamous divisions related to the concept of notoro. Ntoro is one of the two great elements in every individual, with bogya (blood) the other. While ntoro is transmitted patrilineally, bogya is passed through the female line. The ntoro divisions inform practices such as taboo observances and ritual activity. Key features of Ashanti religion (at the time this entry focuses on) include various supernatural beings, ritual objects, practitioners, and ceremonies. The supreme high god is known as Nyame, God of the Sky, Supreme Being of the Universe. Nyame is generally viewed as far removed from the daily life of the Ashanti but delegates some powers to other beings. Additionally, lesser deities are known as abosom, and ancestral spirits are known as samanfo. Other minor spirits, powers of nature, and beings such as fairies (mmoatia) and forest monsters (sasabonsam) are present. Certain objects are of religious significance, including obosom and suman. An obosom is a non-human spirit's resting place, a shrine, usually consisting of a brass pan or bowl containing objects. Human spirits (ancestral spirits) are believed to inhabit objects as well, namely blackened stools. These stools were anointed during ceremonies and received offerings and sacrifices. Suman is the term to describe objects such as charms, amulets, talismans, mascots, or fetishes, which are imbued with supernatural or magical powers. Specialized religious practitioners are known as okomfo (priests). These individuals experience contact with a deity, and subsequently, enter a period of training before becoming an official priest of that particular deity. A variety of rituals and ceremonies were practiced, many of which centered around the propitiation of specific deities or ancestral spirits (such as formal clan leaders or royalty). Because religion was important to nearly all aspects of life, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with society itself.

Date Range: 1880 CE - 1910 CE

Region: Kumasi, Ashanti Region, Ghana, ca. 1895

Region tags: Africa, Western Africa, Ghana

Kumasi, Ashanti Region, Ghana, ca. 1895

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Divale, W. (2004). Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.
- Source 2: Murdock, G.P. & Wilson, S.F. (Jul., 1972). Settlement patterns and community organization: Cross-Cultural Codes 3. *Ethnology*, 11(3), 254-295.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=fe12-001>
- Source 1 Description: Rattray, R. S. (Robert Sutherland). (1923). *Ashanti*. Clarendon Press.
- Source 2 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=fe12-002>
- Source 2 Description: Rattray, R. S. (Robert S. (1927). *Religion and art in Ashanti*. Clarendon Press.
- Source 3 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=fe12-000>
- Source 3 Description: Gilbert, M., Lagacé, R. O., & Skoggard, I. (2000). Culture summary: Akan. HRAF.
- Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=fe12-003>
- Source 1 Description: Rattray, R. S. (Robert S. (1929). *Ashanti law and constitution*. Clarendon Press.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Y a-t-il d'autres groupes religieux en contact culturel avec la religion cible:

– Yes

Notes: At the time this entry focuses on, the British held control over the area (see Gilbert, Lagacé, & Skoggard, 2000). Gilbert, Lagacé, & Skoggard (2000) note that "the Akan [larger cultural group to which the Ashanti belong] have largely been Christian since the nineteenth century...European Christian missions were highly successful." However, the principal ethnographic authority (Rattray, 1923:139) notes "...I am convinced that the conception, in the Ashanti mind, of a Supreme Being has nothing whatever to do with missionary influence, nor is it to be ascribed to contact with Christians or even, I believe, with Mohammedans."

Y a-t-il un conflit violent (à l'intérieur de la région échantillon):

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1649, Frequency of Internal Warfare (resolved rating), "internal warfare seems to be absent or rare" (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Y a-t-il un conflit violent (avec les groupes à l'extérieur de la région échantillon):

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1650, Frequency of External Warfare (resolved rating), "external warfare seems to occur once every 3 to 10 years" (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Est-ce que le group religieux possède un processus ou un système pour déterminer l'appartenance religieuse:

– Yes

Notes: Because religion permeates all aspects of life, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with Ashanti society itself. Therefore, membership is the default.

↳ Déterminée par la naissance (l'appartenance est par défaut au sein de cette société):

– Yes

Notes: Because religion permeates all aspects of life, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with Ashanti society itself. Therefore, membership is the default.

Est-ce que le groupe fait activement du prosélytisme et recrute de nouveaux membres:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the Ashanti would actively proselytize and recruit new members.

Est-ce que le groupe religieux reçoit du support politique officiel:

– Yes

Notes: Because religion permeates all aspects of life, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with Ashanti society itself. In this way, religion is considered to have official political support. Furthermore, those in leadership roles (such as clan rulers) are propitiated after death, showing a connection between political leadership and the supernatural. The spirits of deceased clan rulers are propitiated during the Adaye ceremonies, which occur twice every 43 days (see Rattray, 1923:92).

↳ Le code juridique du régime politique coïncide presque parfaitement avec le code religieux:

– Yes

Notes: "At the outset [of fieldwork] I [author] came to suspect, what later on I was to discover to be an indisputable fact, namely, that Ashanti Law and Ashanti Religion were intimately associated" (Rattray, 1929:v).

Y a-t-il une conception de l'apostasie dans la religion:

– I don't know

Size and Structure

Y a-t-il des leaders reconnus au sein du groupe religieux:

– Yes

Notes: "From the information at our disposal, we now know that the Ashanti makes a distinction between the following: the okomfo (priest); the sumankwafo or dunseni (the medicine-man); and the

Bonsam komfo (witch-doctor). The word okomfo, without any further qualification refers to a priest of one of the orthodox abosom (gods)" (Rattray, 1927:39).

↳ Les leaders religieux sont choisis:

– Yes

Notes: "Most, if not all, Ashanti priests and priestesses will state that the reason they first adopted their profession was because they discovered that they were subject to possession by some spirit influence...The subject of these fits would then probably decide, or be persuaded, to enter and train for the priesthood, and would therefore enter the service of some full-fledged priest of the particular god, whose spirit he has been told has manifested itself in him" (Rattray, 1927:40).

Scripture

Est-ce que le groupe religieux possède des écritures:

"Écritures" est un terme générique qui désigne des textes vénérés qui sont particulièrement considérés sacrés et comme detenant une autorité par rapport à d'autres textes. À proprement parler, ce terme fait référence à des textes écrits mais il existe également des "écritures orales" (par exemple: Les Védas en Inde)

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of scripture.

Architecture, Geography

L'architecture monumentale religieuse est-elle présente:

– No

Notes: According to Murdock and Wilson (1972) Column 6: Large or Impressive Structures, "there are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings."

Existe-t-il différents types d'architecture monumentale religieuse:

– Yes

Notes: See the questions below for more information regarding different types of religious architecture.

↳ Tombes:

– Yes

Notes: "These eight rooms at Bantama [site of the royal mausoleum], with their eight skeleton occupants, waited upon by their eight 'wives', became the centre and prototype of the cult which venerates and propitiates the spirits of ancestors" (Rattray, 1927:120).

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: "Besides these [Sky God] altars, are to be found, hidden away in remote corners of the older palaces, beautifully designed temples to the Sky God" (Rattray, 1923:142).

Autels:

– Yes

Notes: "But it is hardly an exaggeration to say that every compound in Ashanti contains an altar to the Sky God, in the shape of a forked branch cut from a certain tree which the Ashanti call 'Nyame dua, lit. God's tree. Between the branches, which are cut short, is placed a basin, or perhaps a pot, and in this receptacle is generally to be found (besides the offering) a neolithic celt ('Nyame akuma, God's axe)" (Rattray, 1923:141).

L'iconographie est-elle présente:

– I don't know

Existe-t-il des sites spécifiquement dédiés aux pratiques sacrées ou considérées comme sacrées:

– Yes

Notes: A specific sacred grove is described by the principal ethnographic authority as "perhaps hold to be the most hallowed spot in all their territory" (Rattray, 1923:121). "At this spot, Ashanti myth declares, the first human beings, belonging to certain of their ruling clans, came forth from the ground, and settling near by, increased and multiplied, learned to use fire and other arts, till eventually, compelled by increasing numbers, they scattered and became the clan or 'blood' from which the rulers of the united nation later chose their kings and queens" (Rattray, 1923:121).

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: A specific sacred grove is described by the principal ethnographic authority as "perhaps hold to be the most hallowed spot in all their territory" (Rattray, 1923:121).

Les pèlerinages sont-ils présents:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of pilgrimages.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

La distinction corps-esprit est-elle présente:

Répondez "non" seulement si la qualité de personne (ou conscience) s'éteint avec la mort du corps physique. Répondre "oui" ne signifie pas nécessairement qu'il existe une dualité cartésienne corps/esprit mais que certains éléments de la qualité de personne (ou conscience) demeurent après la mort du corps.

– Yes

Notes: "The Ashanti use a number of names which have been roughly translated into English by the words 'soul' or 'spirit' or 'ghost'..." (Rattray, 1927:152). "The destination of these souls after death is important. The mogya or abusua, the blood and body soul, which gives persons their bodily form, becomes on death a saman (ghost, spirit ancestor), retains its bodily form, and goes to live in the spirit world to await a chance of reincarnation through some woman of its own blood (clan)" (Rattray, 1927:319).

L'esprit est conçu comme étant non-matériel et ontologiquement différent du corps:

– Yes

Notes: "It is a man's sunsum that may wander about in sleep" (Rattray, 1927:154).

Croyance en la vie après la mort:

– Yes

Notes: "For not only are human beings divided into exogamous clans and ntoro, but in the spirit world (samando) the ghosts continue to be concerned with and able not only to confer good upon, but to receive benefits from, those members of the human community alone who were their clansmen on earth" (Rattray, 1923:80).

Réincarnation dans ce monde:

– Yes

Notes: "Okra: The Soul of a man. According to the notions of the natives the kara of a person exists before his birth and may be the soul or spirit of a relation or other person already dead. In life the 'kra is considered partly as the soul or spirit of a person (cf. sunsum, honhom), partly as a separate being, distinct from the person, who protects him...When the person is about to die, the kara leaves him gradually, before he breathes his last..." (Rattray, 1927:153).

Dans une forme humaine:

– Yes

Notes: "The destination of these souls after death is important. The mogya or abusua, the blood and body soul, which gives persons their bodily form, becomes on death a saman (ghost, spirit ancestor), retains its bodily form, and goes to live in the spirit world to await a chance of reincarnation through some woman of its own blood (clan)" (Rattray, 1927:319).

Dans une forme animale ou végétale:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates a belief that reincarnation takes place in animal or plant form; only human forms of reincarnation are described.

↳ Dans la forme d'un ou des objets inanimés:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates a belief that reincarnation takes place in the form of inanimate objects; only human forms of reincarnation are described.

↳ Dans une forme non individuelle (c'est-à-dire sous forme, par exemple, de renaissance collective, de tribu ou de lignée familiale, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: "The destination of these souls after death is important. The mogya or abusua, the blood and body soul, which gives persons their bodily form, becomes on death a saman (ghost, spirit ancestor), retains its bodily form, and goes to live in the spirit world to await a chance of reincarnation through some woman of its own blood (clan)" (Rattray, 1927:319).

↳ Réincarnation liée à une notion de causalité transcendante (par exemple: karma):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates that reincarnation is linked to a notion of life-transcending causality, such as karma.

Y a-t-il des traitements spéciaux pour le corps des membres du groupe religieux:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more detail regarding the treatment of the deceased.

↳ Crémation:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of cremation.

↳ Momification:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of mummification.

↳ Inhumation:

– Yes

Notes: "The original type of Ashanti grave was an oblong pit, on one side of which a niche, called ahyenemu, was excavated, above the level of the floor, sufficiently large to receive the body. This niche was then screened off with a mat and the rest of the cavity filled in...The motive in making such a grave is undoubtedly the reluctance to pour earth over the face and body of the dead, who has to be made as comfortable as possible. The introduction of coffins in Ashanti is altering this type of grave to the ordinary pit" (Rattray, 1927:162).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Le corps est fléchi (les jambes sont pliées ou le corps est recroquevillé):

– Yes

Notes: "The body was placed in the niche, lying on its left side, with the legs slightly drawn up, and hands palms together, under the left cheek, often with a handkerchief between them; the face was covered" (Rattray, 1927:162).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Le corps est tout droit à la verticale (où le corps est enterré en position debout):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating corpses were interred in an upright position.

↳ Cannibalisme:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of cannibalism.

↳ Exposition à des éléments (par exemple: séché à l'air):

– Yes

Notes: "Here [at the Asonyeso, burial place of kings] for eighty days and nights the body lay in a coffin, which rested on supports and was placed above a pit..." (Rattray, 1927:114). The final preparations for burial we then made for the body.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite

↳ Donné à manger aux animaux:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating corpses were fed to animals.

↳ Inhumation secondaire:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1850, Secondary bone/body treatment (original scale), "secondary contact with the body or bones of the deceased does not occur" (Schroeder, 2001; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Traitement secondaire du corps:

– Yes

Notes: "Here [at the Asonyeso, burial place of kings] for eighty days and nights the body lay in a coffin, which rested on supports and was placed above a pit...On the eightieth day the corpse was removed, and the process of disintegration hastened by scraping the remaining flesh from

the bones, which were finally oiled with buffalo fat, or with 'the Queen's fat', all the saman (talisman) worn during life being fastened on the proper bones. The long bones were then articulated with flat gold wire" (Rattray, 1927:114). The bones were then placed in a coffin for burial (see Rattray, 1927, 114).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite

Y a-t-il présence de co-sacrifices lors d'inhumations dans des tombes ou lors d'enterrements:

– Yes

Notes: "After a priest has been buried, a sheep is sacrificed over the shrine of his particular god 'to prevent the saman (ghost) taking his nkomoa to the spirit world'" (Rattray, 1927:176).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Des humains:

– Yes

Notes: After the death of a king, the Queen Mother "dispatched messengers to the royal harem, for certain of the late king's wives to prepare themselves to accompany their husband on the journey upon which he had set out. The king, before his death, might have informed the Queen Mother which of his women he wished to go with him, and she also might choose others for this privilege. Others again would volunteer to share their fate" (Rattray, 1927:108).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite

↳ Des humains en dehors du groupe sont sacrifiés:

– I don't know

↳ Des humains au sein du groupe sont sacrifiés:

– Yes

Notes: After the death of a king, the Queen Mother "dispatched messengers to the royal harem, for certain of the late king's wives to prepare themselves to accompany their husband on the journey upon which he had set out. The king, before his death, might have informed the Queen Mother which of his women he wished to go with him, and she also might choose others for this privilege. Others again would volunteer to share their fate" (Rattray, 1927:108). "...the four classes of victims—criminals, captives of war, volunteers, and various holders of offices at court, who did not seem to have any say in the matter..." (Rattray, 1927:109).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite

↳ D'autres humains sont sacrifiés [spécifiez]:

– I don't know

Des animaux:

– Yes

Notes: "After a priest has been buried, a sheep is sacrificed over the shrine of his particular god 'to prevent the saman (ghost) taking his nkomoa to the spirit world'" (Rattray, 1927:176).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Les biens funéraires sont-ils présents:

– Yes

Notes: "The body, dressed in its best cloth and adorned, in addition to the 'soul money' [ornaments bound to the wrists of the corpse], with every available gold ornament, is laid on its left side, generally with the hands folded against the cheek, and sometimes with a silk handkerchief between them..." (Rattray, 1927:149).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Autre [précisez]:

– Yes

Notes: Food is placed with the deceased (see Rattray, 1927:156-157).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Est-ce que les enterrements formels sont présents:

– Yes

Notes: "The body is generally buried on the third day (ayi yo da)...Coffins nowadays are quite common. They were used in olden times, as we have seen, in the case of kings. They are said to have been fashioned out of the great flat buttress roots of the onyina (silk-cotton tree). When a coffin was not used, the body was wrapped in mats" (Rattray, 1927:159). For a description of funeral practices of kings see Rattray, 1927 pp. 104-121; general population pp.147-174; priests pp.176-176.

Comme cénotaphe:

– I don't know

Dans un cimetière:

– Yes

Notes: See Rattray, 1927, p. 118 & 160.

↳ Tombe-crypte familiale:

– I don't know

↳ Domestique (les individus sont enterrés sous la maison ou dans des endroits utilisés pour la conduite d'activités domestiques normales):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates that the deceased were interred in domestic spaces.

↳ Autre [précisez]:

– Yes [specify]: Barim (mausoleum)

Notes: Prior to 1895, kings were interred within the Barim (mausoleum), for their final resting-place (see Rattray, 1927:117).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1800 BCE - 1895 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite

Supernatural Beings

Est-ce que les êtres surnaturels sont présents:

– Yes

Notes: "In the latter category [non-human spiritual powers] are included all deities, from the Supreme Being, 'Nyame or Nyankopon, who dwells somewhat aloof in His firmament, down to those to whom He delegates some of His powers, as His vice-regents upon Earth. There are the lesser gods, who in their turn are graded in a regular descending scale, until they reach, or at times almost merge into, that class which the Ashanti themselves name suman, who are among the lowest grades of superhuman powers" (Rattray, 1923:86).

↳ Un dieu supérieur suprême est présent:

– Yes

Notes: "...I [Rattray] am convinced that the conception, in the Ashanti mind, of a Supreme Being has nothing whatever to do with missionary influence, nor is it to be ascribed to contact with Christians or even, I believe, with Mohammedans" (Rattray, 1923:140).

↳ Le dieu supérieur suprême est une déité associée avec le ciel:

– Yes

Notes: "...'Nyame, the God of the Sky, who is to [the Ashanti] the Supreme Being of the Universe" (Rattray, 1923:90).

↳ Le dieu supérieur suprême est une divinité chthonienne (monde des morts):

– No

Notes: The supreme high god is described as a sky god (see Rattray, 1923:90).

↳ Le dieu supérieur suprême est en fusion avec le monarque (roi = dieu supérieur):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of a belief that the supreme high god is fused with the monarch.

↳ Le dieu supérieur suprême est en relation de parenté avec les élites:

– I don't know

↳ Le dieu supérieur suprême incontestablement bon:

– I don't know

↳ Le dieu supérieur suprême détient une efficacité causale délibérée dans le monde:

– No

Notes: "It is not, however, the Sky and the Earth deities who in Ashanti are held to be the prime factors in shaping and influencing the actions and destinies of mankind. These great unseen powers are generally too remote or perhaps too mighty to be concerned very intimately with the individual clan, much less with the individual member of that clan, and the predominant influences in the Ashanti religion are neither 'Saturday Sky-god' nor 'Thursday Earth-goddess', nor even the hundreds of gods (abosom), with which it is true the land is filled, but are the samanfo, the spirits of the departed forbears of the clan" (Rattray, 1923:216).

↳ Le dieu supérieur suprême détient une efficacité causale indirecte dans le monde:

– Yes

Notes: "...Nyame, the Sky God, is considered too remote to be concerned very directly in person with the affairs of man, and has delegated His powers to His lieutenants, the abosom, or lesser gods" (Rattray, 1923:141).

↳ Le dieu supérieur suprême manifeste des émotions positives:

– I don't know

↳ Est-il permis de porter une dévotion à des êtres surnaturels différents du dieu supérieur:

– Yes

Notes: According to an informant, "We in Ashanti dare not worship the Sky God alone,

or the Earth Goddess alone, or any one spirit. We have to protect ourselves against, and use when we can, the spirits of all things in the Sky and upon Earth" (in Rattray, 1923:150).

↳ Le dieu supérieur suprême communique avec les vivants:

– No

Notes: The supreme high god is viewed as remote and generally removed from the everyday lives of human (See Rattray, 1923:216).

↳ Est-ce que des esprits qui étaient auparavant humains sont présents:

– Yes

Notes: "Saman. This is a ghost, an apparition, a spectre; this term is never applied to a living person or to anything inherent in a living person. It is objective and is the form which the dead are sometimes seen to take, when visible on earth, and in it they go about in the asaman or samandow (the place of ghosts); samanpow is the 'thicket of ghosts'; Samanfo, the ghosts, i. e. spirits of ancestors" (Rattray, 1927:152).

↳ Des esprits humains peuvent être vus:

– I don't know

↳ Est-ce que les esprits qui étaient auparavant humains détiennent une connaissance de ce monde:

– Yes

Notes: "When the late omanhene (paramount chief) of [not specified] was ill, a priest consulted by the family as to the cause is reported to have said that the spirits of the sick man's ancestors were annoyed because he, the omanhene, had been heard to say that he had done more for 'the stool' than they had ever done. In consequence, said the priest, the spirits were calling upon him to account for his words" (Rattray, 1923:138).

↳ Les esprits humains détiennent une efficacité causale délibérée dans le monde:

– Yes

Notes: "'The reason that a man might not be killed without first being told what he had done to deserve death was because, if he were executed without a trial, his sasa (ghost) would trouble the Chief in his sleep and also the people in the town.' We have seen how this fear of a dead man's sasa was present in a minor degree, even in the case of a prisoner duly executed by a strictly legal process" (Rattray, 1929: 295).

↳ Les esprits humains peuvent récompenser:

– I don't know

↳ Les esprits humains peuvent punir:

– Yes

Notes: See Rattray, 1929:295

– No

Notes: It appears that human spirits are capable of having deliberate causal efficacy in the world, but such actions are not described in relation to specific punishment or reward. Rather, human spirits' causal efficacy appears to come from general vindictiveness or neutrality. "The ghost can, if vindictive, make a man impotent, or a woman barren; it can hasten death; it can interfere with the crops. All the prayers and petitions addressed to it for these blessings, therefore, really amount to a request that it should be passive and neutral, or at any rate should not interfere with what might otherwise turn out successfully. 'Give us children' is the polite way of saying 'do not exercise your evil power and make us unfertile'" (Rattray, 1927:182).

↳ Les esprits humains détiennent une efficacité causale indirecte dans le monde:

– Yes

Notes: "The stool, which during the life-time of its possessor [referring to a clan ruler] was so intimately bound (literally and metaphorically speaking) with its owner's sunsum or soul, thus becomes after death a shrine into which the departed spirit may again be called upon to enter on certain special occasions, such as those about to be described [the Adae ceremony], that it may receive that adulation and those gifts that were dear to it in life, and so be induced to continue to use its new and greater spiritual influence in the interest of those over whom it formerly ruled when upon earth" (Rattray, 1923:92).

↳ Les esprits humains possèdent une mémoire de la vie:

– Yes

Notes: "For not only are human beings divided into exogamous clans and ntoro, but in the spirit world (samando) the ghosts continue to be concerned with and able not only to confer good upon, but to receive benefits from, those members of the human community alone who were their clansmen on earth" (Rattray, 1923:80).

↳ Les esprits humains manifestent des émotions négatives:

– Yes

Notes: The following quote describes human spirits as capable of exhibiting vindictiveness. "The ghost can, if vindictive, make a man impotent, or a woman barren; it can hasten death; it can interfere with the crops" (Rattray, 1927:182).

↳ Des êtres surnaturels non-humains sont présents:

– Yes

Notes: "...other minor spirits, or powers of nature, are not wholly ignored or neglected, and that all are considered as able in some manner to help the greater spirit that is to be called upon to guide and assist mankind" (Rattray, 1923:149).

↳ Ces êtres surnaturels peuvent être vus:

– Yes

Notes: "If there is one kind of supernatural manifestation of which the average Ashanti is more firmly convinced than another, it is his belief in the existence of the mmoatia, the little folk, the fairies. He believes in them 'because he has seen them'" (Rattray, 1927:25).

↳ Des êtres surnaturels non-humains détiennent une efficacité causale délibérée dans le monde:

– Yes

Notes: "The offenses...known in Ashanti as Oman Akyiwadie, which, translated literally, means, 'Things hateful to the Tribe'. These acts were looked upon as sins of which the central authority was bound to take immediate official notice, lest certain supernatural powers, to whom the deeds were regarded as peculiarly offensive, should wreak their vengeance upon those whose paramount duty it was to protect their interests and to punish breaches of immemorial law or custom" (Rattray, 1929:294).

↳ Ces êtres surnaturels peuvent récompenser:

– I don't know

↳ Ces êtres surnaturels peuvent punir:

– Yes

Notes: "The offenses...known in Ashanti as Oman Akyiwadie, which, translated literally, means, 'Things hateful to the Tribe'. These acts were looked upon as sins of which the central authority was bound to take immediate official notice, lest certain supernatural powers, to whom the deeds were regarded as peculiarly offensive, should wreak their vengeance upon those whose paramount duty it was to protect their interests and to punish breaches of immemorial law or custom" (Rattray, 1929:294).

↳ Des êtres surnaturels détiennent une efficacité causale indirecte dans le monde:

– Yes

Notes: "A man or woman who is ill may also consult a priest of one of the many abosom (gods) as to the nature, cause, and probable ending of his sickness, and in many cases is informed by the god, through the medium of its mouthpiece the priest, that ' samanfo ye fwe fwe wo' ('the spirits of your ancestors are seeking for you'). This affords us a further clue as to another possible source of sickness and death"(Rattray, 1927:148).

↳ Ces êtres surnaturels manifestent des émotions positives:

– I don't know

↳ Ces êtres surnaturels manifestent des émotions négatives:

– I don't know

↳ Des êtres à la fois divins et humains sont présents:

– I don't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: "In the [non-human supernatural being] category are included all deities, from the Supreme Being, 'Nyame or Nyankopon, who dwells somewhat aloof in His firmament, down to those to whom He delegates some of His powers, as His vice-regents upon Earth. There are the lesser gods, who in their turn are graded in a regular descending scale, until they reach, or at times almost merge into, that class which the Ashanti themselves name suman, who are among the lowest grades of superhuman powers" (Rattray, 1923:86).

↳ Organisé par la parenté basée sur un modèle familial:

– Yes

Notes: "There is known, from one end of Ashanti to the other, a popular myth...This myth recounts how 'Nyame—the Sky God—had various sons of whom one in particular was a bayeyere (favourite son). 'Nyame decided to send these children of his down to the earth in order that they might receive benefits from, and confer them upon, mankind. All these sons bore the names of what are now rivers or lakes..." (Rattray, 1923:145).

↳ Organisé hiérarchiquement:

– Yes

Notes: "In the [non-human supernatural being] category are included all deities, from the Supreme Being, 'Nyame or Nyankopon, who dwells somewhat aloof in His firmament, down to those to whom He delegates some of His powers, as His vice-regents upon Earth. There are the lesser gods, who in their turn are graded in a regular descending scale, until they reach, or at times almost merge into, that class which the Ashanti themselves name suman, who are among the lowest grades of superhuman powers" (Rattray, 1923:86).

Supernatural Monitoring

La surveillance surnaturelle est-elle présente:

"Surveillance surnaturelle" désigne la surveillance effectuée par des êtres surnaturels des comportements et/ou pensées des humains plus particulièrement en ce qui a trait aux normes sociales ou aux potentielles violations des normes.

– Yes

Notes: "The offenses...known in Ashanti as Oman Akyiwadie, which, translated literally, means, 'Things hateful to the Tribe'. These acts were looked upon as sins of which the central authority was bound to take immediate official notice, lest certain supernatural powers, to whom the deeds were regarded as

peculiarly offensive, should wreak their vengeance upon those whose paramount duty it was to protect their interests and to punish breaches of immemorial law or custom" (Rattray, 1929:294). Rattray (1929:294) describes a list of 11 Oman Akyiwadie. Because these actions are said to offend supernatural beings, this list of Oman Akyiwadie is assumed to be the actions supernatural beings care about.

↳ Il existe une surveillance surnaturelle veillant à l'adhésion aux normes, en particulier:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: See Rattray, 1929:294

↳ Les êtres surnaturels se soucient des tabous:

– Yes

Notes: One of the Oman Akyiwadie is described as "The violation, by word or deed, of any other recognized Tribal taboo" See Rattray, 1929:294

↳ De la nourriture:

– I don't know

Notes: Not specified

↳ Des endroits sacrés:

– I don't know

Notes: Not specified

↳ Des objets sacrés:

– I don't know

Notes: Not specified

↳ Les êtres surnaturels se préoccupent du meurtre des coreligionnaires:

– Yes

Notes: Murder is listed as an Oman Akyiwadie. The type of murder is not specified but is presumed to be the murder of in-group individuals (see Rattray, 1929:294).

↳ Les êtres surnaturels se préoccupent du sexe:

– Yes

Notes: "A class of 'sins' which we might describe as 'sexual offenses', and others of a somewhat similar nature, which we should consider possibly as 'immoral' but not as 'criminal'" (Rattray, 1929:294).

↳ Adultère:

– Yes

Notes: "...adultery with another man's wife, but only in certain specific cases, or under certain particular circumstances" (Rattray, 1929:304).

↳ Inceste:

– Yes

Notes: Rattray, 1929:304

↳ Autre déviance sexuelle [précisez]:

– Yes [specify]: Sexual intercourse with a girl before she reaches puberty

Notes: See Rattray, 1929:298

↳ Les êtres surnaturels se préoccupent de la sorcellerie:

– Yes

Notes: See Rattray, 1929:294

↳ Les êtres surnaturels se préoccupent des combats non mortels:

– Yes

Notes: See Rattray, 1929:294

↳ Les êtres surnaturels se préoccupent des crimes contre les biens:

– Yes

Notes: See Rattray, 1929:294

↳ Les êtres surnaturels se préoccupent d'autres choses [spécifiez]:

– Yes [specify]: Suicide

Notes: See Rattray, 1929:294

– Yes [specify]: Treason and cowardice

Notes: See Rattray, 1929:294

– Yes [specify]: The invocation of a curse upon a Chief

Notes: See Rattray, 1929:294

Est-ce que les êtres surnaturels infligent des punitions:

– Yes

Notes: "The offenses...known in Ashanti as Oman Akyiwadie, which, translated literally, means, 'Things hateful to the Tribe'. These acts were looked upon as sins of which the central authority was bound to

take immediate official notice, lest certain supernatural powers, to whom the deeds were regarded as peculiarly offensive, should wreak their vengeance upon those whose paramount duty it was to protect their interests and to punish breaches of immemorial law or custom" (Rattray, 1929:294). "These cases [of disputes] were of two kinds, each of an entirely different nature, but here classed together, as their commission equally necessitated the immediate interference of the central authority. The motives for this interference were in both cases identical, and might be summed up in the phrase 'the necessity for the self-preservation of the kindred group'. The sanctions which necessitated this interference were dissimilar; in one case pressure was imposed by human beings, in the other by spiritual agencies" (Rattray, 1929:285).

↳ Est-ce que la cause ou l'agent de la punition surnaturelle sont connus:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural punishment is done by a variety of supernatural beings. See questions below.

↳ La punition est infligée uniquement par un dieu supérieur:

– No

Notes: The supreme high god is generally removed from the affairs of everyday human life. Supernatural punishment is done by a variety of supernatural beings. See questions below.

↳ La punition est infligée par plusieurs êtres surnaturels:

– Yes

Notes: "The offenses...known in Ashanti as Oman Akyiwadie, which, translated literally, means, 'Things hateful to the Tribe'. These acts were looked upon as sins of which the central authority was bound to take immediate official notice, lest certain supernatural powers, to whom the deeds were regarded as peculiarly offensive, should wreak their vengeance upon those whose paramount duty it was to protect their interests and to punish breaches of immemorial law or custom" (Rattray, 1929:294).

↳ Autre [précisez]:

– Yes

Notes: It appears that human spirits are capable of having deliberate causal efficacy in the world, but such actions are not described in relation to specific punishment or reward. Rather, human spirits' causal efficacy appears to come from general vindictiveness or neutrality. "The ghost can, if vindictive, make a man impotent, or a woman barren; it can hasten death; it can interfere with the crops. All the prayers and petitions addressed to it for these blessings, therefore, really amount to a request that it should be passive and neutral, or at any rate should not interfere with what might otherwise turn out successfully. 'Give us children' is the polite way of saying 'do not exercise your evil power and make us unfertile'" (Rattray, 1927:182).

↳ Est-ce que la raison de la punition surnaturelle est connue:

– Yes

Notes: See the questions below for more information regarding the reasons for supernatural punishment.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: "The offenses...known in Ashanti as Oman Akyiwadie, which, translated literally, means, 'Things hateful to the Tribe'. These acts were looked upon as sins of which the central authority was bound to take immediate official notice, lest certain supernatural powers, to whom the deeds were regarded as peculiarly offensive, should wreak their vengeance upon those whose paramount duty it was to protect their interests and to punish breaches of immemorial law or custom" (Rattray, 1929:294).

↳ Autre [précisez]:

– Yes

Notes: It appears that human spirits are capable of having deliberate causal efficacy in the world, but such actions are not described in relation to specific punishment or reward. Rather, human spirits' causal efficacy appears to come from general vindictiveness or neutrality. "The ghost can, if vindictive, make a man impotent, or a woman barren; it can hasten death; it can interfere with the crops. All the prayers and petitions addressed to it for these blessings, therefore, really amount to a request that it should be passive and neutral, or at any rate should not interfere with what might otherwise turn out successfully. 'Give us children' is the polite way of saying 'do not exercise your evil power and make us infertile'" (Rattray, 1927:182).

↳ Les punitions surnaturelles sont infligées dans la vie après la mort:

– I don't know

↳ Les punitions surnaturelles sont infligées dans cette vie même:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more details regarding supernatural punishment in this lifetime.

↳ Les punitions dans cette vie prennent la forme de mauvaises récoltes ou de mauvaise température:

– Yes

Notes: "The ghost can, if vindictive, make a man impotent, or a woman barren; it can hasten death; it can interfere with the crops. All the prayers and petitions addressed to it for these blessings, therefore, really amount to a request that it should be passive and neutral, or at any rate should not interfere with what might otherwise turn out successfully. 'Give us children' is the polite way of saying 'do not exercise your evil power and make us infertile'" (Rattray, 1927:182).

↳ Les punitions dans cette vie prennent la forme d'incapacité à se reproduire:

– Yes

Notes: "The ghost can, if vindictive, make a man impotent, or a woman barren; it can hasten death; it can interfere with the crops. All the prayers and petitions addressed to it for these blessings, therefore, really amount to a request that it should be passive and neutral, or at any rate should not interfere with what might otherwise turn out successfully. 'Give us children' is the polite way of saying 'do not exercise your evil power and make us infertile'" (Rattray, 1927:182).

Autre [précisez]:

– Yes

Notes: "The reason that a man might not be killed without first being told what he had done to deserve death was because, if he were executed without a trial, his sasa (ghost) would trouble the Chief in his sleep and also the people in the town.' We have seen how this fear of a dead man's sasa was present in a minor degree, even in the case of a prisoner duly executed by a strictly legal process" (Rattray, 1929: 295).

Est-ce que les êtres surnaturels confèrent des récompenses:

– I don't know

Notes: It appears that human spirits are capable of having deliberate causal efficacy in the world, but such actions are not described in relation to specific punishment or reward. Rather, human spirits' causal efficacy appears to come from general vindictiveness or neutrality. "The ghost can, if vindictive, make a man impotent, or a woman barren; it can hasten death; it can interfere with the crops. All the prayers and petitions addressed to it for these blessings, therefore, really amount to a request that it should be passive and neutral, or at any rate should not interfere with what might otherwise turn out successfully. 'Give us children' is the polite way of saying 'do not exercise your evil power and make us infertile'" (Rattray, 1927:182). "For not only are human beings divided into exogamous clans and ntoro, but in the spirit world (samando) the ghosts continue to be concerned with and able not only to confer good upon, but to receive benefits from, those members of the human community alone who were their clansmen on earth" (Rattray, 1923:80).

Messianism/Eschatology

Est-ce qu'il y a présence de croyances messianiques:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of messianic beliefs.

Est-ce qu'il y a présence d'une eschatologie:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of a belief in an eschatology.

Norms and Moral Realism

Y a-t-il une distinction entre conventions et morale au sein du groupe religieux:

– Yes

Notes: The principal ethnographic authority, Rattray, describes different types of offenses, such as Tribal or National taboos versus household offenses (see Rattray, 1929:285).

↳ Quelle est la nature de cette distinction:

– Present and clear

Notes: "...those two main divisions of offences which the Ashanti alone seemed formerly to recognize, i. e. Oman Akyiwadie (Tribal taboos or sins), and Efiesem (literally, cases [that might be settled] in the house)" (Rattray, 1929:293).

↳ Y a-t-il des normes morales spécifiques prescrites par le groupe religieux:

– Yes

Notes: "The offenses...known in Ashanti as Oman Akyiwadie, which, translated literally, means, 'Things hateful to the Tribe'. These acts were looked upon as sins of which the central authority was bound to take immediate official notice, lest certain supernatural powers, to whom the deeds were regarded as peculiarly offensive, should wreak their vengeance upon those whose paramount duty it was to protect their interests and to punish breaches of immemorial law or custom" (Rattray, 1929:294).

↳ Y a-t-il des normes morales spécifiques prescrites par le groupe religieux:

– Yes

Notes: "These cases [of disputes] were of two kinds, each of an entirely different nature, but here classed together, as their commission equally necessitated the immediate interference of the central authority. The motives for this interference were in both cases identical, and might be summed up in the phrase 'the necessity for the self-preservation of the kindred group'. The sanctions which necessitated this interference were dissimilar; in one case pressure was imposed by human beings, in the other by spiritual agencies" (Rattray, 1929:285).

↳ Des normes morales spécifiques sont liées explicitement à de vagues entités métaphysiques:

– Yes

Notes: "The offenses...known in Ashanti as Oman Akyiwadie, which, translated literally, means, 'Things hateful to the Tribe'. These acts were looked upon as sins of which the central authority was bound to take immediate official notice, lest certain supernatural powers, to whom the deeds were regarded as peculiarly offensive, should wreak their vengeance upon those whose paramount duty it was to protect their interests and to punish breaches of immemorial law or custom" (Rattray, 1929:294).

↳ Il n'existe pas de normes morales spécifiques qui entretiennent des liens particuliers avec le monde métaphysique:

– No

↳ Les normes morales s'appliquent à:

– All individuals within society

Notes: See Rattray, 1929:293-294.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Est-ce que l'appartenance à ce groupe religieux requiert le célibat (abstinence sexuelle complète):

– No

Notes: A widow must remain celibate for a year following the death of her husband (see Rattray, 1927:171). However, this practice appears to be a specific taboo, rather than a requirement for membership.

Est-ce que l'appartenance à ce groupe religieux pose des contraintes sur les relations sexuelles (abstinence sexuelle partielle):

– I don't know

Est-ce que l'appartenance à ce groupe religieux requiert la castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of required castration.

Est-ce que l'appartenance à ce groupe religieux requiert de faire des jeûnes:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of required fasting.

Est-ce que l'appartenance à ce groupe religieux requiert la renonciation à des occasions de manger (tabous sur de la nourriture désirée):

– Yes

Notes: "Every obosom (god) has its list, long or short, of Akyiwadie, or taboos or avoidance [including certain foods], but it would scarcely be correct to label these animals or things as totems of the obosom and thus of the persons serving that obosom" (Rattray, 1923:49).

Est-ce que l'appartenance à ce groupe religieux requiert des cicatrisations permanentes ou des altérations corporelles douloureuses:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of required permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations.

Est-ce que l'appartenance à ce groupe religieux requiert de mettre le corps dans des positions douloureuses ou le soumettre à des blessures douloureuses passagères:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of required painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds.

Est-ce que l'appartenance à ce groupe religieux requiert de sacrifier des adultes:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Yes

Notes: Human sacrifice does not appear to be required for group membership. However, there is evidence for human sacrifice during the funeral ceremonies of kings. "It was incumbent upon those left on earth to see that the king entered the spirit-world with a retinue befitting his high station. Such killings thus became a last pious homage and service to the dead" (Rattray, 1927:105).

↳ Étrangers, esclaves:

– Yes

Notes: "...the four classes of victims—criminals, captives of war, volunteers, and various holders of offices at court, who did not seem to have any say in the matter..." (Rattray, 1927:109).

↳ Commun des mortels:

– Yes

Notes: "...the four classes of victims—criminals, captives of war, volunteers, and various holders of offices at court, who did not seem to have any say in the matter..." (Rattray, 1927:109).

↳ Élite

– Yes

Notes: "...the four classes of victims—criminals, captives of war, volunteers, and various holders of offices at court, who did not seem to have any say in the matter..." (Rattray, 1927:109).

Est-ce que l'appartenance à ce groupe religieux requiert de sacrifier des enfants:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Yes

Notes: Human sacrifice does not appear to be required for group membership. However, there is evidence for human sacrifice during the funeral ceremonies of kings. Following the death of a king, "representatives of each section of household office-holders were killed in order to accompany the king; these included many young boys to act as elephant-tail switchers and heralds" (Rattray, 1927:109). An informant (in Rattray, 1923) discussed having witnessed a child sacrifice upon the Cyabom fetish 20 years ago (around 1901) during the ceremony of Wukudae (see p. 100). Wukudae is one of the ceremonies of Aadae, which involves the propitiation of deceased clan rulers' spirits.

↳ Étrangers, esclaves:

– No

Notes: See Rattray, 1927:109

↳ Commun des mortels:

– I don't know

↳ Élite

– I don't know

Est-ce que l'appartenance à ce groupe religieux requiert le sacrifice de soi (suicide):

– No

Notes: "Suicide, except under certain peculiar circumstances, was formerly regarded in Ashanti as a capital sin...Not all forms of what we would term 'suicide' were regarded as sins; in fact, under certain circumstances, the action of taking one's own life was considered as honourable and acclaimed as praiseworthy; e. g. to kill oneself in war...rather than fall into the hands of the enemy or return home to tell of a defeat; to take one's own life in order to accompany a beloved master or mistress to the land of the spirits; and finally, those especially interesting cases, where a man commits suicide to wipe out what he considers his dishonour and because he cannot stand the ridicule of his companions" (Rattray, 1929:299).

Est-ce que l'appartenance à ce groupe religieux requiert de participer à des rituels à grande échelle:

[c'est-à-dire, impliquant la participation de deux foyers ou plus; cela inclut les "cérémonies" et les "festivals" à grande échelle]

– Yes

Notes: Large-scale rituals, such as ceremonies and festivals, are present and important to social and religious life. Although participation is not explicitly described as required, these events are important and widely participated in. Rituals and ceremonies are described in detail within Rattray, 1923; 1927.

↳ En moyenne, pour les rituels à grande échelle, combien de participants se rassemblent à un endroit:

– I don't know

Notes: The number of participants varies according to the specific ceremony. For example, ceremonies in connection with the sacred grove (see Rattray, 1923:121) involve a smaller group of priests and leaders, while the Adaye ceremony involves the entire community (see Rattray, 1923:92).

↳ Quelle est la moyenne de temps d'intervalle entre deux performances (en heures):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– I don't know

↳ Y a-t-il des vérifications de l'orthopraxie:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: A professionalized priesthood leads large-scale rituals (e.g., during the Adae ceremony; see Rattray, 1923:92).

↳ Y a-t-il usage de substances intoxicantes:

– Yes

Notes: Alcoholic beverages are used during a variety of large-scale ceremonies, such as the Adae ceremony. The Adae ceremony is conducted to propitiate the spirits of deceased clan rulers (see Rattray, 1923:92).

Est-ce que des marqueurs extra-rituels sont présents au sein du groupe:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more detail regarding extra-ritual in-group markers.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Cheveux:

– Yes

Notes: "These priests, who are dedicated to 'Nyame [supreme high god] for life, cut their hair in a peculiar manner, the head being shaved save for a patch on the sides and down the middle. White clay is then smeared in three lines on the bald patches" (Rattray, 1923:143).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

Quel est le meilleur qualificatif pour décrire la société à laquelle appartient le groupe religieux (s'il-vous-plaît, ne faites qu'un choix):

– A chiefdom

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 237, Jurisdictional Hierarchy Beyond Local Community, there are two levels of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, indicative of a larger chiefdom.

Source of information: Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variable 237.

Education

Est-ce que le groupe religieux fournit une éducation formelle à ses membres:

– I don't know

Notes: Education is not described by the principal ethnographic source (Rattray, 1923).

Public Works

Est-ce que le groupe religieux en question fournit un espace public pour l'entreposage des aliments:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004), food is stored in individual households.

Est-ce que le groupe religieux en question fournit une infrastructure de transport:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 14, Routes of Land Transport (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004), unimproved trails are utilized. Presumably, transportation infrastructure is not present.

Enforcement

Est-ce que le groupe religieux en question fournit une force policière institutionnalisée:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 90, Police, indicates that police were not specialized among the Ashanti (Tuden and Marshall, 1972; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Written Language

Est-ce que le groupe religieux en question possède sa propre langue écrite:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 149, Scale 1 [of cultural complexity] Writing and Records, indicates that writing and records were not utilized by the Ashanti (Murdock and Provost, 1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Calendar

Est-ce que le groupe religieux en question détient un calendrier formel:

– I don't know

Food Production

Est-ce que le groupe religieux en question fournit de la nourriture pour lui-même:

– Yes

Notes: The Ashanti relied predominantly on extensive or shifting agriculture. Hunting and fishing supplements the diet. Source of information: Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

S'il-vous-plaît, caractérisez les formes ou le niveau de production alimentaire (sélectionnez tous les choix qui s'appliquent):

- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: The Ashanti relied predominantly on extensive or shifting agriculture. Hunting and fishing supplements the diet. Source of information: Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.